

Mike Long

THE INSTITUTION OF ENGINEERS OF IRELAND

RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN DRIVEN PILE DESIGN:

Shaft capacities of piles in clay

BARRY M. LEHANE BE, DIC, PhD, MIEI
Dept. of Civil Engineering, Trinity College

Paper presented to the Geotechnical Society
of the Institution of Engineers of Ireland
10th January 1995

*Paper submitted to
Civil Board for
Review 6/12/94*

Glenbeigh Records
Management

F3265149

SYNOPSIS

The alpha (total stress) method is the most popular means of assessing the shaft capacity of driven piles in clay. The paper examines this method in the context of some recent research into the mechanisms and soil parameters controlling driven pile behaviour. The alpha method is initially reviewed before describing the main trends of behaviour that have become evident from the results of carefully instrumented test piles and a new theoretical approach. These results show that the behaviour of driven piles can be described and understood far more satisfactorily within an effective stress framework.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

It has proved difficult to develop a practical unified theory for pile design and, as a result, a great diversity of empirical approaches are presently in use. The α method is by far the most popular means of assessing the shaft capacity of piles in Ireland. However, this method like the other approaches, has a less than one in two probability of consistently predicting the shaft capacity to within 50% of the actual capacity (Briaud & Tucker 1988).

The profession has dealt with this poor predictive performance by conducting site specific pile tests and using the results from these tests, in conjunction with local experience (e.g. pile set criteria), to aid the design of piles at that site. This approach may be uneconomic for small contracts and where there are a large variety of pile types at a given site. These points aside, it is essential that we have rational means of estimating pile capacities at the scheme design stage and when pile test results are extrapolated for the design of the contract piles.

This paper examines the α method in the context of recent research into the performance of driven piles. The method is first described and some of its practical limitations are outlined. The findings of theoretical and experimental studies are then summarised and it is shown how they lead to a framework for an effective stress approach for pile design. This approach is subsequently compared with the α method and shown to provide a far more rational description of the processes controlling shaft capacity.

All notation is, for convenience, summarised in Table 2 at the end of this paper.

2.0 THE α METHOD

2.1 Evolution and current status

In the early stages of the development of modern day soil mechanics, it was considered that the ultimate average shear stress that can be mobilised along the shaft of a driven pile (τ_{av}) should be equivalent to the (undisturbed) average undrained shear strength of the clay, $(c_u)_{av}$. However analyses of results from load tests on piles tested to failure, such as those conducted by Tomlinson (1957), indicated that τ_{av} was generally less than $(c_u)_{av}$. The ratio $\tau_{av}/(c_u)_{av}$, termed the adhesion factor (α), displayed a tendency to reduce with increasing undrained strength; this phenomenon was attributed tentatively to the larger degree of disturbance caused by the driving process in stiff clays.

As our understanding of soil properties improved, it became evident that the value of 'undrained strength' (c_u) depends, amongst other things, on the

sample quality and the test method. Dennis & Olsen (1983) concluded that the inconsistency of the procedures used to determine c_u was the primary reason for the large scatter in the α values deduced in previous correlations and proposed the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_{av} &= \alpha (c_{u0})_{av} \\ &= \alpha F_c (c_u)_{av}\end{aligned}$$

The factor, F_c , corrects the measured c_u value to the equivalent quick undrained triaxial compression strength (c_{u0}) of high quality samples i.e. $F_c c_u = c_{u0}$. High quality samples were assumed to be those retrieved by thin wall pistons with a diameter greater than 75mm. The correlation deduced by Dennis & Olsen is shown on Figure 1 and indicates α reducing from 1.0 at $c_{u0} \approx 30\text{kPa}$ to a minimum value of 0.3 for $c_{u0} \geq 250\text{kPa}$.

Parametric studies by Semple & Ridgen (1984) and others showed a better fit to the available data base could be obtained by relating

Figure 1 Variation of α proposed by Dennis & Olsen (1983).

α with the undrained strength ratio c_{u0}/σ'_{v0} . This is the approach currently proposed by the American Petroleum Institute (API) which in 1989 recommended the following correlations:

$$\alpha = 0.5 (c_{u0}/\sigma'_{v0})^{-0.5} \quad \text{for } c_{u0}/\sigma'_{v0} \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

$$\alpha = 0.5 (c_{u0}/\sigma'_{v0})^{-0.25} \quad \text{for } c_{u0}/\sigma'_{v0} > 1 \quad (2)$$

Tang (1988) showed that these recommendations were a significant improvement on previous API ' α methods'. Furthermore, they reflect some trends of behaviour which have been measured in high quality instrumented pile tests (discussed below).

2.2 Limitations of the α method

The α method's popularity arises because of its simplicity. However it is important that we are aware of its in-built assumptions and limitations. Some of these are outlined below.

(i) Designers have always understood that there are a large number of factors affecting shaft capacity. These include soil type, pile length, pile type and geometry, installation method, set-up time, loading history, loading direction and load test procedure. However, because of the large number of influential variables and the relatively sparse data base of well documented pile tests, the reported empirical correlations for α represent little more than trend lines drawn through poorly correlated scatter diagrams.

(ii) Because few piles have been instrumented to measure the variation of local shear stresses along pile shafts, the backfigured α values are average values for the complete shaft. The applicability of

Figure 2 Stages in the life of a driven pile.

the α method in multi-layered deposits must therefore be in considerable doubt, as would α values backfigured from tests in such deposits.

(iii) The α method cannot be used to assess the stresses acting on the pile shaft. Without knowledge of these stresses, prediction of pile behaviour under service loads and more complicated load sets is not possible. In addition, any extrapolation of the results from one pile test to the design of another pile cannot be done in a rational manner.

It is in the light of these and other difficulties that theoretical and experimental studies on driven pile behaviour have recently been initiated.

3.0 SUMMARY OF RECENT RESEARCH

3.1 Introduction

Offshore piles are often up to 2m in diameter and over 80m in length. The impracticalities of load testing such piles provided much of the recent impetus towards the development of more soundly based design methods. It was clear to the offshore industry that

greater confidence in design could only be achieved if the mechanics of pile behaviour were understood (at least qualitatively) and could be explained within a rational soil mechanics framework. Soil behaviour is governed by *effective stresses* and therefore a rational theory for pile behaviour must be able to predict the effective stresses in the soil surrounding the pile and particularly at the pile-soil interface. As illustrated in Figure 2, predictions must take account of the changing conditions associated with the four stages in the life of a driven pile: (a) prior to installation, (b) during installation, (c) equalisation (consolidation) and (d) during the static/dynamic loading applied by the structure (shearing). Of these four stages, development of a realistic theoretical method to model the installation process has proved to be the most elusive.

The main thrust of recent research into driven piles has focused on the use of carefully instrumented field displacement piles that were capable of measuring the radial effective stresses acting at various positions on the pile shaft during each stage in the life of a pile. Tests with these piles have allowed some of the main parameters controlling shaft

capacity to be identified. In parallel with this experimental work, Baligh, Whittle and others at MIT (Boston) have developed a promising theoretical method that aids the assessment of the shaft capacity of driven piles. This method, although having some inherent weaknesses, predicts similar patterns of behaviour to those found in the instrumented pile tests.

3.2 THEORETICAL RESEARCH

3.2.1 Installation predictions

Many geotechnical problems such as those involving retaining walls, slopes or shallow foundations can relate the stresses in the ground directly to the depth of overburden and the applied loads. Pile installation, however, induces strains in the ground that are almost completely dependent on the boundary conditions (e.g. the shape of the pile) and effectively independent of the type of soil and the depth of overburden. This 'strain controlled' condition makes the calculation of stresses acting on a pile highly indeterminate.

Baligh (1985) was the first to propose a reasonably realistic method for estimating the strains (and hence stresses) induced in the ground by pile installation. This method, which is referred to as the Strain Path Method (SPM), assumes that the soil moves relative to the pile tip in the same way that an incompressible, inviscid fluid would flow around the tip. In other words, the action of pile installation is considered to be analogous to the 'flow of soil' around a pile fixed in space.

A clear picture of the process of 'closed-ended' pile installation, as predicted by the SPM, is shown on Figure 3. This figure plots the

Figure 3 Strain Path Method (SPM) prediction for the strain paths followed by soil elements adjacent to a closed-ended driven pile in clay.

variations of the vertical strain (ϵ_1), the cavity expansion strain (ϵ_2) and the simple shear strain (ϵ_3) experienced by three soil elements (A,F,G) as each passes the pile tip during installation. It is evident that:

- Each component of strain has its maximum when the soil element is at a different location relative to the pile tip.
- Strains increase until the soil elements are at or close to the pile tip but decrease with continued penetration.
- The large strain levels to which the elements are subjected

indicate that the post-peak behaviour of the soil has an important influence on installation behaviour.

Whittle (1987) developed a very sophisticated soil model, referred to as MIT-E3, for the specific purpose of estimating stresses from these particularly complex strain characteristics. Predictions for the stresses induced by pile installation displayed very similar trends to those observed in the field although the absolute magnitudes of the stresses predicted, especially in dilatant clays, were in error by up to $\approx 50\%$.

Figure 4 Excess pore pressures and radial effective stresses predicted by SPM after pile installation.

A typical example of the SPM predictions using the MIT-E3 soil model for the stresses surrounding a pile just after installation in a lightly overconsolidated (contractant) clay is shown on Figure 4. Points to note include:

- There are significant gradients of excess pore pressure ($u - u_0$) and radial effective stress (σ'_r) close to the pile tip, but these reduce in intensity with distance from the tip.
- Radial effective stresses (σ'_r) at the pile shaft are appreciably less than the initial undisturbed horizontal stress (σ'_{h0}) which is $0.7\sigma'_{v0}$ for the case analysed on this figure. σ'_r increases with r/R and is comparable to σ'_{h0} at $r/R \approx 5$.
- At locations above the pile tip, pore pressure ratios, $(u - u_0)/\sigma'_{v0}$, remain constant from $r/R = 1$ to $r/R \approx 2$ and then reduce to about 20% of these values at $r/R \approx 10$.

An important consequence of the soil flow analogy adopted in the SPM is that scale effects can be removed by normalising distances with respect to the pile radius (R). For example, the stresses or displacements evaluated at a given normalised radial distance from the centreline (r/R) and height above the tip (h/R) are independent of the pile radius. This result was used in the development of the effective stress approach described in Section 3.4.

3.2.2 Equalisation predictions

The effective stresses in the soil surrounding a pile change after installation, as excess pore pressures dissipate. It has been shown by Kavvas (1982), and others, that use of a comprehensive soil model and a consolidation theory that models the interaction of the soil skeleton and pore water during dissipation is vital to the prediction of effective stress changes during

equalisation. The accuracy of predictions is also of course strongly dependent on the stress regime assumed to exist after installation. Simple linear analyses (i.e. those assuming a constant coefficient of consolidation) are only adequate for the prediction of the rate of pore water dissipation.

The pore pressures generated during pile installation are a combination of (i) the positive pressures induced by the increase in mean total stress (caused by the physical insertion of the pile in the clay mass) and (ii) those associated with shearing of the soil, which may be positive or negative - depending on the clay type. These two components lead to the contrasting pore pressure responses seen in Figure 5 during the initial stages of equalisation in London Clay and Bothkennar clay.

In the lower OCR Bothkennar clay, shear induced pore pressures are predicted to be positive. These add to those induced by the increase in mean stress with the result that, on completion of installation, pore pressures are predicted to reduce with distance from the shaft (e.g. as in Figure 4). Consequently, a monotonic decrease of pressure during equalisation is observed on Figure 5.

In contrast, large *negative* shear induced pore pressures are predicted close to the pile shaft during installation in the London Clay. However, at a short distance from this zone of intense shearing, positive pressures associated with the increase in mean stress are larger than the (negative) shear induced pressures. As a consequence, the highest water pressures on completion of installation are not at the pile shaft - but at a short distance from the

Figure 5 SPM/MIT-E3 predictions for the stress changes during equalisation; see top legend for definition of equalisation factors for pore pressure, radial effective stress and radial total stress.

shaft. This pressure distribution leads to a flow of water towards the pile (and rise in pressure at the shaft) over the early stages of equalisation. Pressures at the shaft subsequently reduce monotonically as water flows radially outwards.

Figure 5 also shows that:

- Radial total stresses reduce during equalisation. This reduction is far more significant in the low OCR Bothkennar clay.
- Radial effective stresses reduce during the early stages of equalisation in the London Clay (as pore pressures increase) and then

Figure 6 SPM/MIT-E3 predictions for undrained pile loading.

increase to final values that are about 20% higher than those predicted during installation. The increase in σ'_r is much larger in Bothkennar Clay, where equalised stresses are about five times larger than installation stresses.

3.2.3 Predictions for pile loading

Predictions made for the variation of shear stress with radial effective stress (τ_{rz} vs. σ'_r) during undrained pile loading are shown on Figure 6 for Boston Blue clay (BBC), Bothkennar clay (BC) and London Clay (LC). The stress regime predicted in SPM/MIT-E3 analyses for the end of equalisation was used as the initial starting point in the analyses. The variations have been normalised by the pre-loading (equalised) radial effective stress (σ'_{rc}) and indicate:

- reductions in σ'_r in the low OCR Bothkennar and Boston Blue clays, giving σ'_r values at peak shear stress that are $\approx 75\%$ of their initial σ'_{rc} values. Little change in σ'_r is predicted for pile loading in London Clay.
- obliquities at peak shear stress (δ_p) of $\approx 24^\circ$ for all materials, apart from the London Clay at OCR=24 which gave $\delta_p \approx 19^\circ$.

3.3 EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH

Theoretical analyses, such as those described, cannot be validated or improved without reliable field data with which to test their predictions. Until recently, information of this nature was very limited and of poor quality. This situation prompted research institutions such as MIT, Oxford University, NGI and Imperial College to design pile testing instrumentation that would obtain reliable measurements of the effective stresses developed on

Figure 7 The Imperial College instrumented Pile (ICP), showing typical instrument configuration and instrument cluster.

pile shafts during installation, equalisation and load testing to failure. To date, high quality effective stress data have been recorded in fourteen different clay types but in only one sand type.

This section reviews the principal findings of this experimental research by examining the data obtained with the Imperial College instrumented Pile (ICP) at three clay sites: stiff to hard heavily overconsolidated Cowden till and London Clay and soft to firm lightly overconsolidated Bothkennar clay. The reader is referred to Lehane & Jardine (1994a,b) for a more complete description of these case studies.

3.3.1 The Imperial College instrumented Pile (ICP)

The ICP is a 102mm diameter steel tubular pile which is assembled in segments to give a typical total length of $\approx 7\text{m}$ (Figure 7). All ICP's were jacked at a typical rate of 500mm/min to a maximum final penetration of $\approx 6.5\text{m}$.

The instrumented sections (or clusters) were interconnected by casings and a solid 60° cone was fitted at the pile tip. Three instrument clusters (referred to by their height above the pile tip, h , normalised by the pile radius, R , i.e. h/R) were positioned over the lower 3m length of the pile. Each cluster contained (a) an axial load cell, (b) a surface stress transducer (SST) to measure the radial total stress (σ_r) and shear stress (τ_{rz}), (c) a pore pressure unit which houses two diametrically opposite pore pressure probes and (d) a temperature sensor within each SST. Other axial load cells are located $\approx 3.8\text{m}$ from the pile tip and at the pile head.

The instruments were designed to minimise measurement errors due to cell action and time lag effects. The high linearity of their strain-gauged components and the comprehensive calibration procedures adopted ensured that data of the highest quality were obtained. All gauges remained stable throughout testing, showing virtually no zero shift or change in sensitivity.

3.3.2 Pile installation

The experiments with the ICP showed that the radial total stresses developed on the pile shafts during installation (σ_{ri}) depended primarily on (a) the clay's consistency and (b) the particular strain history imposed on the ground by the process of installation. These two effects are illustrated on Figure 8 where, for all depths encountered, the mean ratios of σ_{ri} to q_b (the pile end bearing pressure) are plotted against the relative depth of the pile tip (h/R) at which these ratios were recorded. (Note that q_b values were, in all cases, closely comparable to the CPT end resistance, q_c).

During steady penetration, conditions at the pile tip are comparable to those near an expanding spherical cavity and, to a first approximation, $\sigma_{ri} \approx q_b$. As the tip advances below any given soil horizon (and the relative tip depth, h/R , increases), the stress concentration focused at the tip becomes more remote from the

Figure 8 Variation with h/R of the installation of the radial total stress (σ_r) normalised by pile end bearing ($q_b \approx q_c$).

given soil horizon and the soil at this level unloads radially. σ_r reduces to match the limit pressure for a cylindrical cavity (or pressuremeter test p_{lim} value) when $h/R \approx 3$, and by the time the pile has penetrated further to give a h/R value of 50, σ_r has fallen to between 10% and 30% of its maximum value (q_b).

The pore pressure changes induced during installation also depended on soil consistency and the relative depth of the pile tip, but showed more complicated trends. This was partly because the shear induced component - associated with distortion - depended on the dilatant or contractant nature of the soil and was, in some cases, rate dependent.

The large shear strains imposed by pile installation caused significant de-structuring of the sensitive Bothkennar clay, leading to large reductions in the radial effective stresses (σ'_r) from the initial undisturbed values (σ'_{r0}). In contrast, installation in the

insensitive Cowden till and London Clay caused the radial effective stresses to increase to values far greater than σ'_{r0} .

3.3.3 Equalisation

The radial total stress changes observed during equalisation in each of the three clay types are compared on Figure 9 by plotting the mean variations with time of the relative reductions of the

normalised radial total stress, $H/H_i = (\sigma_r - u_0)/(\sigma_{ri} - u_0)$. It is evident that H/H_i reduced for all cases. Greatest relative reductions took place in the low OCR, sensitive Bothkennar clay where the radial total stress at the end of equalisation was only $\approx 40\%$ of that measured during installation.

Pore pressures rose immediately after installation, giving pronounced short-term maxima before pressures decayed towards hydrostatic values. Drainage was clearly more rapid and three-dimensional near the pile tip.

These radial total stress and pore pressure changes led to the variations of the radial effective stress (σ'_r) with time shown on Figure 10. In this figure, the σ'_r values recorded at all instrument levels are normalised by the corresponding σ'_r values measured after full equalisation (σ'_{rc}). Two important features to note are: (i) the pronounced short-term minimum of σ'_r in the dilatant Cowden till and (ii) the large overall increases in σ'_r during equalisation in Bothkennar clay, the relatively neutral effect in Cowden till and the net reduction of σ'_r in the London Clay.

Figure 9 Normalised radial total stress variation with time after installation.

Figure 10 Normalised radial effective stress variation with time after installation.

3.3.4 Equalised radial effective stress

The available shaft capacity after full equalisation is controlled, to a large extent, by the radial effective stresses acting on the pile at that stage (σ'_{rc}). Figure 11 summarises the σ'_{rc} profiles obtained for piles installed to 6m at all ICP sites (also included is the σ'_{rc} profile measured with the ICP in Labenne sand; see Lehane et al 1993). It is apparent that σ'_{rc} measured at similar depths against identical piles may differ by an order of magnitude, depending on the soil type. A clear hierarchy exists, with the oldest and most heavily overconsolidated clay developing the largest stresses, whilst the young, low OCR Bothkennar clay provides the smallest. The dense, but geologically recent Cowden till generally falls between these two extremes.

As shown on Figure 12, the profiles of σ'_{rc} also varied with pile penetration. It is evident that, at any fixed depth, higher stresses were developed on the 3.5m

length piles than on the piles installed to $\approx 6m$. This is a direct result of the stresses reducing as the relative depth of the pile tip (h/R) increases. Such a dependence was also shown by the installation stresses (see Figure 8) and suggests that shaft capacities vary with pile length in a way significantly different from that assumed in standard pile design methods (e.g. the α method)

3.3.5 Pile response to loading

In all experiments, the peak local shear stress (τ_f) was related to the radial effective stress acting at failure (σ'_{rf}) and the angle of friction at the pile-soil interface (δ_f) through the Coulomb failure criterion:

$$\tau_f = \sigma'_{rf} \tan \delta_f \tag{3}$$

$$= (\sigma'_{rf}/\sigma'_{rc}) \sigma'_{rc} \tan \delta_f \tag{4}$$

Figure 11 Equalised radial effective stress (σ'_{rc}) profiles measured with the ICP at four sites (the material was London Clay at the Canons Park site).

Figure 12 σ'_{rc} profiles measured in Cowden till and Bothkennar clay for piles installed to depths of $\approx 3.5\text{m}$ and 6m .

Typical variations of shear stress (τ_{rz}) and radial effective stress (σ'_r) measured in compression and tension load tests are shown on Figure 13. These 'stress paths' have been normalised by the pre-loading radial effective stress, σ'_{rc} .

It is evident that while there was little change in radial effective stress up to peak capacity, the values of δ_f recorded were very sensitive to the soil and pile types e.g. δ_f varies from $\approx 13^\circ$ in London Clay to $\approx 28^\circ$ in Bothkennar clay. These δ_f angles could, however, be predicted with surprising accuracy from ring shear interface experiments which modelled (i) the displacement and rate history of soil elements adjacent to a shaft during installation (ii) the surface properties of the piles and (iii) the normal effective stress level; e.g. see Lehane and Jardine (1992).

Figure 13 Normalised 'stress paths' measured during pile loading.

3.4 Outcome of research

Most recent research has focused on investigating the most influential parameters affecting the development of shaft capacity on closed-ended driven piles in clay. Both the theoretical and experimental studies (including those conducted by organisations other than Imperial College) have indicated:

1. The radial total stresses developed in a given soil horizon during installation are primarily dependent on the clay's consistency and the height of that horizon above the pile tip (h). Statistical analyses of the complete data base of high quality measurements have indicated that the most consistent trends emerge when the normalised radial total stress ratio is related to the clay's overconsolidation ratio and the relative depth of the pile tip i.e.

$$H_i = (\sigma_{ri} - u_0) / \sigma'_{v0}$$

$$= f(\text{OCR}, h/R) \quad (5)$$

2. Radial total stresses reduce during equalisation as the pore pressures generated by installation dissipate; this reduction reflects the interaction of a yielding zone close to the pile with the surrounding zone of (unyielding) high stiffness clay. Larger relative reductions were measured in lightly overconsolidated clays and those with a high sensitivity (s_r), suggesting that:

$$H_c/H_i = (\sigma_{rc} - u_0) / (\sigma_{ri} - u_0)$$

$$= \sigma'_{rc} / (\sigma_{ri} - u_0)$$

$$= f(s_r, \text{OCR}) \quad (6)$$

3. Peak shear stresses (τ_f) were governed by the simple Coulomb criterion and radial effective stress reduced by about 15% of σ'_{rc} at this peak, implying

$$\tau_f \approx 0.85 \sigma'_{rc} \tan \delta_f \quad (7)$$

$$= (H_i) (H_c/H_i) 0.85 \tan \delta_f \quad (8)$$

Lehane et al (1994) reviewed the full data base of high quality measurements (comprising 14 clay types) and used these three main conclusions to derive the following expression for the maximum shear stress that can be developed adjacent to a driven pile in clay:

$$\tau_f = \sigma'_{v0} \text{OCR}^{0.42} (h/R)^{-0.2}$$

$$\times [1.6 - 0.5 I_{vr}] \tan \delta_f \quad (9)$$

where

- OCR = overconsolidation ratio derived from oedometer tests
- h/R = height above the pile tip divided by the pile radius
- I_{vr} = relative void index, defined as $(e - e_{ICL}) / C_c^*$; note that at low OCR, $I_{vr} \approx \log(s_r / \text{OCR})$.

- e = in-situ void ratio
- e_{ICL} = void ratio at the same vertical effective stress on the 1-D virgin consolidation line of reconstituted material (or intrinsic compression line, ICL)
- C_c^* = slope of the ICL
- δ_f = interface friction angle derived using appropriate ring shear interface tests.

This expression is regarded as provisional in view of the fairly limited data base that was available for its derivation. Nevertheless its usefulness, at present, lies in the fact that in addition to being an 'effective stress' expression (that is in keeping with state-of-the-art theoretical models), it allows the relative effects of the most important factors affecting shaft capacity to be evaluated.

4.0 Evaluation of the α method

The single most conclusive result that emerged from the research summarised above is that pile shaft capacity is controlled by the effective stress conditions acting around the pile. It is instructive, however, at this point to investigate the correspondence of the α method (which is a total stress approach) with the effective stress expression for τ_f (Eqn. 9). This is performed in the following sections by (i) comparing Eqn. 9 with the values of α recommended by API in its most recent formulation i.e. Eqns. 1 and 2 and (ii) comparing predictions for τ_f with that measured by Trinity College in an instrumented driven pile test at Croke Park.

4.1 Comparison between the effective stress method and the API α method

Data reported by Hight et al (1987) indicate that, for most clay soils, the undrained strength ratio for peak shear strengths measured in triaxial compression (c_{u0} / σ'_{v0}) may be approximated by the expression:

$$c_{u0} / \sigma'_{v0} = (0.3 \pm 0.05) \text{OCR}^{0.8 \pm 0.05} \quad (10)$$

It should be noted that this type of relationship is not valid for aged high OCR plastic clays such as London clay which fail in triaxial tests before critical state conditions are reached (due to the formation of shear bands). With this point in mind, the API expressions for α (Eqns. 1 & 2) may be re-written using Eqn. 10 as:

$$\alpha \approx 0.91 \text{OCR}^{-0.4} \text{ for } \text{OCR} \leq 4.5$$

$$\approx 0.68 \text{OCR}^{-0.2} \text{ for } \text{OCR} > 4.5 \quad (11)$$

Values of α are usually backfigured from load tests by dividing the measured ultimate shaft shear stress (τ_{sv}) by the average c_{u0} value along the pile length. In a soil deposit where c_{u0} increases linearly with depth from zero at the ground surface (and OCR, δ_f and I_{vr} are constant), the value of α implied by Eqn. 9 is:

$$\alpha = \tau_{sv} / (c_{u0})_{av}$$

$$= [1 / (L(c_{u0})_{av})] \int_0^L \tau_f dz$$

$$\approx \text{OCR}^{-0.38} (L/R)^{-0.2}$$

$$\times [7.4 - 2.4 I_{vr}] \tan \delta_f \quad (12)$$

The values of α predicted by Eqn. 12 for a pile with a slenderness ratio (L/R) of 75 driven into (i) a

Figure 14 Predicted variations of α with OCR

typical lightly overconsolidated silty clay with $\delta_i = 25^\circ$ and $I_{vr} = +1.25$ and (ii) a typical heavily overconsolidated plastic clay with $\delta_i = 15^\circ$ and $I_{vr} = -1.25$ are compared on Figure 14 with API's recommendations. The agreement between the predicted trend with OCR and API is encouraging. It may be surmised from this comparison that the variation proposed by API is biased towards piles of moderate length in low OCR, moderately sensitive silty clays and high OCR plastic clays.

By varying one of the parameters in Eqn. 12 (i.e. OCR, L/R, δ_i or I_{vr}), it is evident that α reduces by a factor of:

- ≈ 3.5 for an increase in OCR from 1.5 to 30
- ≈ 2.6 for a reduction in δ_i from 25° (typical angle for a low plasticity clay) to 10° (for a high plasticity clay)
- ≈ 1.9 for an increase in I_{vr} from 0.0 to +1.5 (i.e. a significant increase in clay sensitivity)
- ≈ 1.4 for an increase in L/R from 20 to 100

While the effective stress expression for τ_f (Eqn. 9) is in good agreement with the measurements made in all ICP tests, Eqn. 12 under-predicts the values of α measured in the London Clay tests by a factor of 2. This is primarily because the relationship assumed between c_{vo}/σ'_{vo} and OCR (Eqn. 10) is not valid for London clay. α values backfigured from pile tests in the materials such as London Clay will clearly be incompatible with those derived in other materials with a similar c_{vo}/σ'_{vo} value, thereby adding to the difficulties associated with using the α method for pile design.

In summary, although the dependence of α on OCR predicted by Eqn. 12 is in general agreement with the relationship between α and OCR deduced empirically by API (Eqns. 1 & 2), it is evident that this relationship is not unique (or realistic) because of the predicted strong dependence of α on the interface shearing characteristics of the materials (δ_i), the clay sensitivity (s_t) and the pile slenderness ratio (L/R). Eqn. 9 must therefore be seen as a significant improvement on the α method.

4.2 Effective stress method applied to measurements at Croke Park

An instrumented driven pile was recently installed and tested in the Black Boulder Clay at Croke Park. Results from this study are currently being assimilated and will be reported in due course (e.g. Looby et al 1995). The aim here is to compare only one (typical) value of τ_f recorded with that predicted using Eqn. 9.

The 273mm diameter steel closed-ended pile was equipped with axial load cells and pore pressure probes at a number of levels along its shaft. A load test conducted after full equalisation had been achieved indicated that the maximum shear stress that could be mobilised at a depth of ≈ 4.5 m (and h/R ratio of 13) was 200 kPa.

Two oedometer tests and a number of interface shear tests were performed to provide the parameters required for Eqn. 9. The first oedometer test was carried out on an intact sample from 5m depth and was used to establish the value of the OCR; this necessitated the use of a 50mm diameter sample to allow the yield stress (pre-consolidation pressure) to be defined adequately. The second oedometer test was carried out on a reconstituted slurry to determine the value of the relative void index, I_{vr} . Looby (1995) conducted the interface shear experiments and deduced an interface residual friction angle of 32° (at the appropriate stress level and steel surface roughness).

The evaluation of τ_f from Eqn. 9 is set out in Table 1 and is seen to underpredict the measured value of τ_f by just 10%.

σ'_{v0} at 4.5m	≈ 65 kPa
In-situ water content	$\approx 10\%$
In-situ void ratio	≈ 0.27
Yield stress at 5m	≈ 1200 kPa
OCR at 4.5m	≈ 18
e_{ICL}	≈ 0.37
C_c^*	≈ 0.075
l_{vr}	≈ -1.3
$\tan \delta_f$	≈ 0.62

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_f &= \sigma'_{v0} \text{OCR}^{0.42} (h/R)^{-0.2} \\ &\quad \times [1.6 - 0.5 l_{vr}] \tan \delta_f \\ &= [65] [18^{0.42}] [13^{-0.2}] \\ &\quad \times [1.6 + 0.5 \times 1.3] [0.62] \\ &= 183 \text{ kPa (compared to} \\ &\quad \text{measured of 200 kPa)}\end{aligned}$$

Table 1 Derivation of τ_f for Croke Park example

It is difficult to obtain relatively undisturbed U100 samples of Black Boulder Clay to determine c_{u0} and as a consequence Stroud's (1988) empirical correlation suggesting c_{u0} (in kPa) is approximately six times the SPT N value is often used. This correlation would imply an approximate c_{u0} value of 300 kPa given that the mean N value measured between 3 and 6m depth at Croke Park was ≈ 50 . Substitution into the API expression for σ (Eqn. 2) implies an σ value of 0.34 and $\tau_f = 0.34 \times 300 = 102$ kPa (assuming local stresses may also be calculated using Eqn. 2). This τ_f prediction is only about a half of the measured value.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

This paper highlights many of the inadequacies of the σ method for the determination of the shaft capacity of driven piles in clay and will hopefully encourage some degree of restraint in its use.

Both experimental and theoretical research have indicated that the behaviour of displacement piles can be described and understood far more satisfactorily within an effective stress framework. Although the natural processes involved are complex, this research has succeeded in identifying some of the main parameters controlling shaft capacity. A semi-empirical effective stress design method has been proposed. This provides guidance on the relative contribution of each parameter to capacity and may, at this stage, be used with the aid of local experience to extrapolate the results from pile tests to the design of contract piles with different configurations.

The paper also reveals the great benefits that can be reaped from the use of carefully instrumented test piles.

Notation

Undrained strength in triax. compress	c_{u0}
Pile end bearing	q_b
Overconsolidation ratio	OCR
Pile radius	R
Radial distance from pile	r
Relative void index (see Section 2.3)	l_{vr}
Sensitivity (intact/remoulded strength)	s_t
Vertical distance above the pile tip	h
Free field vertical effective stress	σ'_{v0}
Free field horizontal effective stress	σ'_{h0}
Radial total and effective stress	σ_r, σ'_r
Pore and excess pore pressure	$u, \Delta u$
Ambient (hydrostatic) pore pressure	u_0
Local shear stress	τ_{rz}
Average shear stress (over complete shaft)	τ_{av}
Maximum local shear stress	τ_f
Normalised radial total stress, $H =$	$(\sigma_r - u_0)/\sigma'_{v0}$
Excess pore pressure ratio, $\Delta u/\sigma'_{v0} =$	$(u - u_0)/\sigma'_{v0}$
Lateral stress coefficient, $K =$	σ'_r/σ'_{v0}

Table 2 Main notation

Subscripts i, c and f are used to denote values of the respective parameters at the completion of installation, after full equalisation and at peak capacity in load tests respectively. For example, H_i is the value of H after installation, K_c is the value of K at the end of equalisation and K_f/K_c is the ratio of K at peak local shear stress to the equalised K value.

References

- American Petroleum Institute (API), (1989), RP2A: 'Recommended practice of planning, designing and constructing fixed offshore platforms', 18th edition, Washington.
- Baligh M.M. (1985), 'Strain Path Method', J. Geotech. Eng., ASCE 111(9), 1108-1136.
- Briaud J.L and Tucker L.M. (1988), 'Measured and predicted axial response of 98 piles', J. of Geotech. Eng. Div., ASCE, 114(9), 984-1001.
- Dennis N.D. and Olsen R.R. (1983), 'Axial capacity of steel pipe piles in clay', Proc. Conf. on geotech. practice on offshore eng., Austin, Texas, 370-388.
- Hight D.W., Jardine R.J. and Gens A. (1987), 'The behaviour of soft clays', Spec. publ. on 'Embankments on soft clay', Bull. of publ. works research centre, Athens, 33-158.
- Kavvasdas M. (1982), 'Non-linear consolidation around driven piles in clay', PhD Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Ladd C.C., Foott R., Ishihara K., Schlosser F. and Poulos H.G. (1977), 'Stress-deformations and strength characteristics', State-of-the-art report, Proc. 9th Int. Conf. on Soil Mech. and Fdn. Eng., Tokyo, 2, 421-494.

Lehane B.M. and Jardine (1992), 'Residual strength characteristics of Bothkennar clay', *Geotechnique*, 42(2), 363:368

Lehane B.M. and Jardine R.J. (1994a), 'Displacement pile behaviour in glacial clay', *Canadian Geotech. J.*, 31(1), 79-90.

Lehane B.M. and Jardine R.J. (1994b), 'Displacement pile behaviour in a soft marine clay', *Canadian Geotech. J.*, 31(2), 181-191.

Lehane B.M., Jardine R.J., Bond A.J. and Chow F. (1994), 'The development of shaft friction on piles in clay', *Proc. XIII Int. Conf. on Soil Mech. and Fdn. Eng.*, New Delhi, 2, pp473-476.

Lehane B.M., Jardine R.J., Bond A.J. and Frank R. (1993), 'Mechanisms of shaft friction in sand from instrumented pile tests', *J. Geotech. Eng., ASCE*, 119(1), 19-35.

Looby M. (1995), 'Experimental investigations of driven pile behaviour in Dublin boulder clay', MSc thesis (in preparation).

Looby M., Farrell E.R. and Lehane B.M. (1995), 'Instrumented pile tests in Dublin's boulder clay' (to be submitted to *Ground Engineering*).

Semple R.M. and Ridgen W.J. (1984), 'Shaft capacity of driven pipe piles in clay', *Proc. Symp. on codes and standards*, ASCE National Conv., San Francisco.

Stroud M.A. (1988), 'The standard penetration test - its implications and the engineering properties of glacial materials', *Proc. Conf. on Penetration Testing in the UK*, Publ. Thomas Telford

Tang W.H. (1988), 'Offshore axial pile design reliability', Research report for Phase 1 of project PRAC 86-298, Dept. of Civ. Eng., Univ. of Illinois.

Tomlinson M.J. (1957), 'The adhesion of piles driven in clay soils', *Proc. 4th Int. Conf. Soil Mech. & Fdn. Eng.*, London, 2, 66-71.

Whittle A.J. (1987), 'A constitutive model for overconsolidated clays with application to the cyclic loading of friction piles', PhD Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.